

Zinc(II) Complexes

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The powerful chelating ligands ortho-phenanthroline, 2-2' -bipyridyl and 2-picolyamine having N—C—C—N chelating group in common, are known to form mono, bis and tris complexes with metallic elements^{1,3}. While the latter two types are wellknown, few examples of mono complexes have appeared⁴⁻⁷. As a part of investigations on several d¹⁰ metal complexes^{8,9}, this communication describes the syntheses and characterisation of a few four-coordinated mono complexes of bivalent zinc with the ligands, viz., ortho-phenanthroline, 5-nitro ortho-phenanthroline, 2,9-dimethyl ortho-phenanthroline, 2-2' -bipyridyl and 2-picolyamine.

TABLE I

Analyses, Colour and Molar conductance of Zinc(II) Complexes

Compound	Colour	Analytical results			Molar conductance mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹
		% Metal	%Nitrogen	%Halogen	
1. [Zn (o-phen) Cl ₂]	White	Found: 20.4	8.6	22.7	6
		Reqd: 20.5	8.8	22.4	
2. [Zn (nitro-phen) Cl ₂]	White	Found: 17.8	11.7	19.8	5
		Reqd. 18.0	11.6	19.6	
3. [Zn (dime-phen) Cl ₂]	White	Found: 18.6	8.3	20.9	5
		Reqd: 18.8	8.1	20.6	
4. [Zn (bipy) Cl ₂]	White	Found: 22.1	9.7	24.5	5
		Reqd: 22.2	9.5	24.3	
5. [Zn (pic-am) Cl ₂]	White	Found: 26.4	11.6	29.3	10
		Reqd: 26.6	11.4	29.1	

where o-phen=ortho-phenanthroline; nitro-phen=5-nitro-ortho-phenanthroline; dime-phen=2,9-dimethyl-ortho-phenanthroline; bipy=2-2'-bipyridyl and pic-am=2-picolyamine.

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General method of syntheses of the complexes: An ethanolic solution of zinc (II) chloride was treated with the stoichiometric quantities of the appropriate ligand in ethanol. Crystalline compounds separated were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 .

The electrical conductance measurements were performed in acetone with the help of a Philip's Conductivity Bridge and a dipping type cell. The analytical and electrolytic conductance data are included in the table.

The recorded low molar conductance values ($\lambda_M=5-10$ mhos) in acetone are indicative of non-electrolytic nature of the complexes¹⁰. All the complexes are fairly soluble in acetone. Analytical data and diamagnetic nature of the complexes suggest presumably tetrahedral structure for these mono-complexes.

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